

**STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS, DIALOGUE JOURNAL
AND SELF ASSESSMENT: INTERVENTION AND STRATEGIES
FOR ENHANCING WRITING SKILLS**

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Strategic Intervention Materials, Dialogue Journal and Self Assessment: Intervention and Strategies for Enhancing Writing Skills

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Abstract

This paper aimed at determining whether collaborative learning using dialogue journals and independent learning using self-assessment would enhance the writing skills of senior high school learners in Pasig. The research method was a mixed one, utilizing a true experiment for quantitative data and a phenomenological approach for qualitative data with a sample of 80 randomly chosen SHS learners. Quantitative data were derived from the results of the Pre-Test, End of Lesson Assessment (Essay), and Post-Test that were checked using an adopted essay rubric by 3 subject experts. Meanwhile, the qualitative data were attained by conducting semi-structured interviews with 20 participants. The statistical analysis used for the pre-test and post-test was an independent sample t-test and weighed mean for the ELA to analyze whether there was a significant difference in the results of the pre-implementation and post-implementation of the intervention used. Interview responses were analyzed through coding and thematic patterns. The results revealed that the writing skills of both CLG and ILG improved after the experiment, but ILG learners achieved a much higher score than CLG; moreover, although both groups claimed to have enjoyed and profited from cooperative and independent learning, the CLG learners, who collaborated with peers, bewailed the incompetence of some of the peers while the ILG learners, who worked by themselves, admitted that assistance from the teacher or a more competent learner could have been better.

Keywords: *dialogue journals, peer teaching, collaborative learning, independent learning, self-assessment*

Introduction

Writing is a means of transmitting a message to a reader for a purpose. The purposes of writing are to express oneself, to provide information for one's reader, to persuade one's reader, and to create a literary work (Pincas, 1998, as cited in Swandi & Shek, 2017). Indeed, writing is one of the most complex processes because of the different demands and activities that a learner needs to produce a well-written text. Cognitive aspects of writing have received a particular attention, as investigators have attempted to understand the thought processes underlying the compositions of learners (Flower & Hayes, 1981, as cited in Sharp, 2016).

According to Valencia (2020), the Philippine Institute for Development Studies has reported that senior high school (SHS) students, especially those in the public schools, lack the necessary basic competency for the SHS program. Teachers have primarily decried the fact that some learners still struggle to create simple sentences in English, making them incapable of coping with the demands of some subjects.

At Nagpayong Senior High School, most of the subjects being taught demand the use of learners' writing skills most particularly in English and Practical Research subjects. As experienced and assessed by teachers teaching English and Practical Research subjects through a pre-assessment survey, the results revealed that majority of the learners obtained "Fine" which constitute to 85.7% and 14.3% got poor in their initial level of mastery in writing skills.

The lack of mastery in writing is explained in Nunan (1999) stating that the evolutions of writing from a subskill to a main skill has made writing become more complicated; hence, mastering the writing skill becomes a trouble not only for second language users but also for the natives themselves (as cited in Fahmi, 2016).

Aside from their poor writing skills, they also have different needs and schema in writing; hence, teachers have a difficult time in helping them (C.M. Olesco, Personal Communication, 2021).

Also, according to Reyes (2015), the reason behind their inefficiency in writing is because the knowledge needed in composition writing was not fully ingrained in their earlier years of schooling, thus, making it difficult for them to make effective English compositions.

Since most learners cannot generate fresh ideas for effective writing in either second or foreign language, several learning strategies have been implemented to increase their efficiency in writing. An extensive amount of research claims that training students to use different kinds of strategies and being aware of their uses enable them to become better language learners (Arulselvi, 2016). There is a high demand for writing strategies that can help them improve their writing performance.

It is in this context the researchers thought of investigating which approach or strategy could better help the learners in constructing effective compositions and improve their writing skills that can greatly help them actively comply in their subject requirements that require intensive writing skills and increase passing rate.

Research Questions

This study aimed at determining whether the use of Strategic Intervention Materials in collaborative learning applying dialogue journal and independent learning applying self-assessment would enhance the Senior high school learners' writing skills and experiences. Specifically, the following questions were answered:

1. What are the scores in essay writing of the following groups of learners in the pretest and post-test and end of lesson assessment:
 - 1.1. collaborative-learning group; and
 - 1.2. independent-learning group?
2. Is there a statistical difference in the scores in pretest and post-tests between the two groups before and after the intervention?
3. What perception do the learners have with regard to essay writing prior to the use of intervention?
4. How do the interventions help enhance the writing skills and perception of the learners using?
 - 4.1. dialogue- journal strategy for the collaborative learning approach;
 - 4.2. self-assessment strategy for the independent-learning approach; and
 - 4.3. strategic Intervention Materials (SIM)?
5. What action plan could be made based on the results of the study?

Literature Review

As stated by Firm (2018), there is a need to change the way educators teach to better reflect the ways students learn, and that is to bring the 5C's into the classroom. Educators should focus on the 5 Cs—collaboration, communication, creativity, and critical and character to foster greater learning. The 5C's is also one of the priority agenda of DepEd in teaching and learning during this remote learning platform.

According to Laal (2012), collaborative learning is a teaching and learning approach involving groups of learners working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product.

Meanwhile, a dialogue journal is a written conversation in which a learner and another learner or teacher communicate regularly [daily, weekly, or on schedule that fits the educational setting] over a semester, school year or course (Peyton, 2000, as cited in Rana, 2018).

Linnell (2010) mentioned three key advantages of using dialogue journals. First, dialogue journals are powerful instruments for coping with the complexities of large classrooms. Second, the more experienced and capable learners can communicate with the entire class and share their life experiences and socio-cultural backgrounds that could educate the other students. Third, dialogue journals can be good places for second-language students to acculturate, assimilate, and adapt.

On the other hand, independent learning is characterized as learning in which learners can make the decisions necessary to meet their own learning needs in collaboration with relevant others (Cukurova, 2014).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used mixed method because the research questions could not possibly be answered by either quantitative or qualitative method alone. Mixed method is a research approach in which researchers collect and analyze both quantitative and qualitative data within the same study (National Collaborating Centre for Methods and Tools, as cited in Shorten & Smith, 2017).

The quantitative part was a true experimental study with randomized subjects. True experiment is used to describe studies with at least one independent variable that is experimentally manipulated and one dependent or outcome variable (Salkind, 2010). In this study, there were two groups, namely, the collaborative group—the experimental group, and the independent-learning group—the control group. The pretest and posttest for both groups, which were narratives / essays, were evaluated using an adopted essay evaluation rubric.

The qualitative part was used to answer Question 4 of the Statement of the Problem. Qualitative research is aimed at developing a thorough understanding of the social world by attempting to learn about the perspectives of people (Chavan & Kemparaj, 2013); it is intended to collect data for learning about the participants, which may be in words or pictures (Creswell & Plano, 2011).

The type of qualitative approach used in this study was phenomenology. The phenomenological research design refers to the study of past experience that requires an explanation or interpretation of the meaning of a certain phenomenon experienced by the participants (Padilla-Díaz, 2015; Creswell & Plano, 2011). Phenomenology was applicable to the present research because it utilized technology-mediated semi-structured interviews to gain an in-depth understanding of the participants' lived experiences in the collaborative- and independent-learning setup.

Participants

The participants of the study are selected grade 11 and grade 12 Senior High School learners from the Humanities and Social Science

(HUMSS) strand, and Accountancy and Business Management (ABM) Strand enrolled in Nagpayong Senior High School for the second semester of School Year 2021-2022.

For this study the researchers have identified 80 learners from each of the strands handled by the researchers.

A convenience sampling technique was used to select the members of the sample. This technique was used because of the relative advantage of ease, time and cost it presents specially this time of pandemic.

The chosen sample were divided into two using simple random sampling: the collaborative-learning group (CLG, the experimental group) and the independent-learning group (ILG, the control group.) Moreover, 20 learners (ten from each group) became the participants for the interview.

Instruments

The researchers facilitated a triangulation using the data sources enumerated above for further verification and validation of the effectiveness of the intervention.

For the quantitative data, the research tool is a rubric that the researchers' adopted from Hsu's study (2017), "Input and Uptake in High School EFL Students' Multiple-Draft Writing Process: A Case Study of a Taiwanese High School EFL Classroom." The rubric is divided into five parts: (a) content; (b) organization; (c) grammar and syntax; (d) vocabulary and spelling; and (e) format. This instrument is used to measure the respondents' levels of mastery in writing their essays for both pretest and posttest.

Using an adopted rubric, the pretest and posttest essays were checked by at least 3 master teachers or subject expert wherein scores are averaged to minimize subjectivity.

For the qualitative data, the researcher randomly select 10 learners from two groups to become participants for the qualitative part of the study. The 20 participants are interviewed separately via Facebook messenger and google form. Their answers are coded and categorized using thematic analysis.

Procedure

For the quantitative data—the true experiment, the 80 respondents are divided into two groups—collaborative-learning group (CLG) and individual-learning group (ILG). The researchers randomly select 40 learners for each group via drawing lots. The 40 learners from CLG are randomly paired with one another. The CLG is assigned as the experimental group, and the ILG is the control group.

All 80 respondents were asked to write a narrative/essay about their research experience in just 100 words in two to three paragraphs for their pretest, their first writing activity for the experiment. Their outputs are checked using the adopted rubric by three master teachers or Subject experts and scores were gathered by the researchers. For emphasis, all these pre and post-test activities and other strategies are done during the COVID-19 post-pandemic through virtual classes using Facebook messenger and google meet.

After the pretest, meetings are held every Friday and Saturday. The researcher taught both groups the meaning, uses, and importance of peer teaching, dialogue journals, and self-assessment. The researchers have also developed a validated strategic intervention material containing lessons on grammar and content, organization, and vocabulary in writing an essay while using Dialogue journals and Self-assessment.

For the qualitative data, results are labelled and categorized using thematic analysis through Philip Adu's (2019) coding and categorizing of qualitative data that involve the following seven steps: (a) changing the 4th specific question of the Statement of the Problem (SOP) to anchor code; (b) getting phrases or clauses from the interview transcripts to obtain answers for the anchor code; (c) using descriptive phrases to label or initially code the extracted answers; (d) gathering the related initially coded answers into groups or categories; (e) using themes to identify the categories; (f) formulating a construct based on the interrelationships of the themes; and (g) producing a graphic representation or model of the construct. Relevant reviews from Chapter 2 are also utilized for data validation.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers themselves explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. They ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Scores in Writing of the Collaborative-Learning Group and the Independent-Learning Group in the Pretest and Posttest

The results revealed that the two groups are both "Fine" in their initial level of mastery in writing skills as indicated by the mean scores, 11.195 for the collaborative-learning group or (CLG), and 10.340 for the individual-learning group or (ILG). As the standard deviation provides information on the dispersion of scores, it is evident that CLG ($SD = 1.98$) has greater variability than ILG ($SD = 1.57$). With "Fine" as level of mastery for both groups, it means that the 80 learners had fair writing skills before the intervention started. They

could speak some English and construct simple sentences, but they need a lot of improvement and mastery in terms of content, organization, grammar and syntax, vocabulary and spelling, as well as the use of proper formats.

Table 1. *Pretest Scores of Collaborative-Learning and Independent-Learning Groups*

Level of Mastery	Collaborative-Learning Group		Independent-Learning Group		Total	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Excellent (19-20)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Very Good (15-18)	1	2.5	4	10.0	5	6.0
Fine (10-14)	26	65.0	33	82.5	59	74.0
Poor (5-9)	13	32.5	3	7.5	16	20.0
Very Poor (0-4)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total	40	100.0	40	100.0	80	100.0
Mean Score	11.195 (Fine)		10.340 (Fine)		10.76 (Fine)	
SD	1.98		1.57		2.14	

According to Reyes (2015), the reason behind their inefficiency in writing is because the knowledge needed in composition writing was not fully ingrained in their earlier years of schooling, thus, making it difficult for them to make effective English compositions.

Table 2. *Posttest Scores of Collaborative-Learning and Independent-Learning Groups*

Level of Mastery	Collaborative-Learning Group		Independent-Learning Group		Total	
	<i>F</i>	%	<i>F</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Excellent (19-20)	1	2.5	6	15.0	7	8.75
Very Good (15-18)	23	57.5	27	67.5	50	62.5
Fine (10-14)	16	40.0	7	17.5	23	28.75
Poor (5-9)	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Very Poor (0-4)	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
Total	40	100.0	40	100.0	80	100.0
Mean Score	14.92 or 15		16.45 or 16		15.68 or 16	
SD	2.03		2.21		2.14	

The results revealed that both groups notch scores within the “Very Good” level of mastery in writing skills as indicated by the mean scores, 14.92 for the collaborative-learning group or (CLG), and 16.45 for the individual-learning group or (ILG). As the standard deviation provides information on the dispersion of scores, it is evident that ILG ($SD = 2.21$) has greater variability than CLG ($SD = 2.03$). The results strongly implied that the majority of students both in the CLG and ILG showed significant progress in terms of the score of their writing. As indicated in the 2 tables presented, the total mean of post-test scores of CLG and ILG of 15.68 is larger than the total mean of pre-test scores which is only 10.76. It indicates that on average, the interventions used caused a significant improvement in students’ scores.

Hasper (2020) cited in her article that helping students develop their knowledge, attitudes, skills and habits, they progressed on the continuum as independent learners. It can be gleaned that the online learning setup, has taught learners to be more responsible and independent in their own education.

Significant Difference in the Scores in Writing Between the Pretests of the Two Groups and Posttests of the Two Groups

Table 3. *t-Test: Comparison of Pretest Scores Between Collaborative-Learning and Independent-Learning Groups*

Group	Means	Standard Dev.	Standard Error	<i>t</i> -ratio	<i>p</i> -value	Decision
Collaborative Learning Group	10.34	8	.2490	2.134	0.36	Not Significant
Independent Learning Group	11.19	1.98	.3138	2.134	0.36	Not Significant

No significant difference is observed between the two groups as revealed by $t = 2.134$, $df = 38$, $p < 0.36$. The probability of error has exceeded than 0.05 criterion set in testing the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the means of scores between groups; hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. It means that the observed difference between the means of CLG (Mean = 10.34, $SD = 1.57$) and ILG (Mean = 11.19, $SD = 1.98$) is not statistically significant and is equal to zero. This suggests that the two groups have the same writing mastery level prior to their exposure to different learning conditions.

To further elaborate this notion, both groups have the same “Fine” level of writing mastery about their knowledge of content, organization, grammar and syntax, vocabulary and spelling, as well as format, prior to the experiment. Based on the features of the level, both groups can write simple sentences and compositions, but they lack the mastery in developing well-written compositions, and they have difficulties in generating the content, organizing their ideas, writing with minimal grammar corrections, and spelling appropriate words.

In table 4, the computed $t = 3.221$, $df = 38$, $p < 0.02$ depicts that there is a significant difference in the means of scores between CLG (Mean = 14.92, $SD = 2.21$) and ILG (Mean = 16.45, $SD = 2.03$); therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Learners who were taught

using the independent-learning approach recorded higher scores than those who were subjected to the collaborative-learning approach.

Table 4. *Independent Sample T-Test: Comparison of Posttest Scores Between Collaborative-Learning and Independent-Learning Groups*

Group	Means	Standard Dev.	Standard Error	t-ratio	p-value	Decision
Collaborative Learning Group	14.92	2.21	.3497	3.221	0.02	Significant
Independent Learning Group	16.45	2.03	.3215	3.221	0.02	Significant

Between the two approaches, it could be implied that the independent-learning approach is considerably more effective than collaborative learning in enhancing learners' writing skills in this time of the pandemic. In conclusion, both interventions have been proven to enhance the writing skills of the learners. Specifically, self-assessment intervention has shown effectiveness for the independent-learning approach, and dialogue journal has also shown effectiveness in enhancing the writing skills of the collaborative learning approach.

Nugroho and Wulandari (2017) explained that the role of learners, is to seek out their own learning resources to resolve their learning difficulties, and teachers are expected to track their students' progress and assist them wherever possible in dealing with their learning difficulties.

The perception of the participants with regard to essay writing prior to the use of intervention

The experiences of the participants before and during the experiment using collaborative learning and independent learning method, serve as an essential part of this research.

Most of participants' responses provide a negative outlook on writing prior to the experiment; thus, the first label/initial code is "frustration, confusion, pressure, nervousness and joy of writing." Their reasons for feeling frustrated when they write range from a lack of prior knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, and the general writing process towards their difficulties in writing, which leads to a negative attitude in writing. This negative mindset demands immediate intervention to motivate students to overcome their hardships.

Some of them, on the other hand, feel the "joy of writing," which stems from the understanding that, as independent writers, they are free to express their emotions and creativity without interference from anyone, including the teacher.

Table 5. *Emerging Themes from the perception of the learners with regard to essay writing prior to the use of intervention and strategies*

Themes/anchor code	Initial codes/ labels	Statements
Attitude towards writing	frustration	Interviewee 1 stated: "Writing is so frustrating... I don't know how to start, but eventually when I learned how things work about writing hindi na sya ganon kahirap since natuto na ako about writing... all thanks to maam kate sa pag turo samin. before kasi I just write and write kahit ano maisip ko but mali pla un because that's not the proper way of writing."
		Interviewee 4 stated: "Frustrating po magsulat kasi sa grammar po nadodoble ko po Kasi ung "and"tsaka po ung "because" tapos po ma'am ung outline po di po ako marunong gumawa."
	confusion	Interviewee 9 stated: "I feel frustrated because I don't have any learning when it comes from writing skills like doing essay but in the end, I feel happy because I can gain and expand my knowledge"
		Interviewee 2 stated: "I'm confused whenever I write. Sa una po maam di ko po alam kung about saan po yung isusulat ko pero pag nakapag focus po ako at may isang idea akong naisip tuloy tuloy na po iyon hanggang sa matapos ko po"
	Pressure in writing	Interviewee 3 stated: "Pressured po ako magsulat. It's hard po magsulat ng essay kasi minsan redundant yung word nagagamit ko kaya nahihirap ako mag sulat ng sentence."
Interviewee 19 stated: "I struggled because my knowledge was limited..."		
nervousness	Interviewee 16 stated: "In general, I feel nervous about writing because in the first place I really do not have the idea and ability to write."	
	joy of writing	Interviewee 6 stated: "I feel great because I can express my feeling thru writing generally."
Interviewee 7 stated: "First of all, I feel great that I'm able to express my thoughts when writing. I've experience getting dizzy and frustrated whenever I think of words that I need to put. I'm excited before we started the action research because I know I able to learn new things and how to this or that."		
Interviewee 11 stated:		

“...I feel amazed and proud of myself because I am able to write it. But I still want improvements that is why I joined this experiment or research.”

Interviewee 13 stated:

“I really enjoy writing because I feel creative whenever I write. I also feel more focused on expressing my thoughts. Sometimes, I feel pressured, but I know that I can finish on time and be satisfied with my work.”

Instead of simply enabling students to write for the sake of creating the required output, Neupane (2014) argues that teachers should incorporate and include students in the entire writing process—preparing, drafting, revising, and rewriting until the final draft is ready for submission. To make writing a meaningful and fruitful experience for students, teachers must encourage them to absorb the important components of the process.

Table 6. *Emerging Themes of Learners perception on how helpful dialogue journal is in enhancing the essay writing skills*

<i>Themes/ anchor code</i>	<i>Initial codes/ labels</i>	<i>Statements</i>
Positive experiences	gaining knowledge from peers,	Interviewee 1 stated: “Yes, it is helpful because through that way I can have the knowledge to change in my writing, what to add, how to improve my writing. Dialogue journals is a good thing that can help someone to improve writing skills just like me. Things really became easy if you have a partner to change dialogues with”.
	establishing connection with peers	Interviewee 8 stated: “Good things that I experienced in using dialogue journals is I was just reminded again about my strengths and weaknesses. I also gained knowledge about my partner’s advice. Because of this, I also got to know my partner better, and we built a relationship with each other.”
	enjoyment of sharing knowledge	Interviewee 5 stated: “Kaya mas gusto ko po talaga ma enhance ang English skills ko lalo na po sa grammar Yes, effective po ma’am sobra po lalo na yng sabi ng partner ko yng mga Mali ko sa grammar, paglagay ng mga comma, at yng steps sa paggawa ng essay.”
	error correction	Interviewee 7 stated: “Mas nalalamaman ko how good she writes and when creating an essay, whether it's a formal essay or narrative. May naishashare din siya na mga bagay na alam niya sa pagsusulat ng essay.” Interviewee 11 stated: “I am not really used working with a partner. I usually do things alone. During the experiment I have a partner, we talk about our works and what are the things needed to change for better results. I feel good working with my partner because we are compatible, and we understand each other. He helps me make my work better, gives suggestion to improve my work and correct me if I'm mistaken.”
Negative experiences	incompetent peers	Interviewee 3 stated: “Parehas po kaming hindi marunong about writing the essay Kaya po kinailangan pa po namin mag research sa internet Ng mga sample about writing the essay”
	difficulty in using the English language	Interviewee 1 stated: “I did encounter problems in dialogue journals because I had a hard time expressing or telling what i feel because we are talking using english laguage...”
	Poor internet connection/ Misunderstandings	Respondent 7 stated: “Having poor internet connection sometimes. Hindi kami magkaintindihan dahil yung ibang messages ko o niya hindi naisensend agad. Tapos, may part na nakulangan ako sa tips niya.For example,nakita ko na may mali akong sentences yet di niya napansin”
	Awkwardness /uneasy feelings towards their partners	Respondent 10 stated: “The difficulty that I experienced in using dialogue journals was when my partner and I first exchanged our work, because first, I'm a little shy about correcting his work. Second, I don't know how to check. And lastly, I'm not good at grammar and essay writing so that I can't perfectly check his work.”.

The participants point out, that during the experiment, they have gained knowledge while establishing a connection with their peers while using dialogue journals. As a result, the researcher uses “gaining knowledge” and “establishing a connection with peers” as the first and second labels. The use of dialogue journals and peer teaching as encouragement and assistance to encourage learners to write more or develop a positive attitude toward writing received positive replies.

The act of acquiring and sharing knowledge has provided the participants with the pleasure of writing, thus the fourth label "enjoyment of sharing knowledge. Another highlight of the study is the fourth category, "error correction," which describes how their friends have assisted them in improving their writing skills. They grow more confident and motivated to write since their peers can give them more concentrated, on-the-spot corrections and provide them with the necessary advice.

Some issues were also encountered by the participants during the experiment. Because some people have been frustrated by being partnered with incompetent peers, the final label, "incompetent peers" and "difficulty in using the English language," were created.

Due to these, the collaborative learners experienced frustration in using dialogue journals with their peers since they have a poor internet connection which leads to failure in communicating effectively to their partner thus the next label “Poor internet connection/ Misunderstandings” was created. Aside from these students were also not very acquainted with their partners since they only communicate online giving them uneasy feelings while interacting with their peers. As a result, the researcher used the last label “Awkwardness/ uneasy feelings towards their partners”.

Table 7. *Emerging Themes of Learners’ perception on how helpful is using self-assessment in enhancing the essay writing skills*

<i>Themes/anchor code</i>	<i>Initial codes/ labels</i>	<i>Statements</i>
Positive experiences	focus on writing,	Interviewee 6 stated: “if my surrounding is very noisy its giving me distraction, too challenging to overcome my difficulties and naoovercome ko naman sya kapag nakapag focus and relax na ako sa pagsusulat mas nag fufunction po utak pag calm lang/i’ll keep myself calm and focus para makapag isip po ako and maexpress ko po ng maayos ung sasabihin ko
	positive outlook on independency of writing,	Interviewee 17 stated: “You will know what’s wrong and right about your essay...they teach us to correct our work in a proper way.”
	overcoming fears of writing	Interviewee 10 stated: “Overall, I’m glad because I’ve learned many things while doing the experiment and also, I’m happy because without this experiment I don’t know how I will overcome some of the parts in our research paper and thankful because this lesson will help me in the next school year.”
	self-improvement/ self-learning suppressed	Interviewee 7 stated: “What really helped me is learning about parallelism by myself. It made me more aware of the grammatical structure of my sentences. Plus, the examples made it more comprehensive.” Interviewee 13 stated: “There are two challenges that I faced during writing activities. First is being consistent in the point of view of my sentence/paragraph. The other is being being sure on the grammar of my work”.
Negative experiences	ideas caused by limited knowledge of grammar and vocabulary	Interviewee 15 stated: “Yes, I encountered many failures, Kasama na po don yong sa grammar and vocabulary. May mga word po ako na nahihirapan i-interpret in English”.
	uncertainty in checking own work	Interviewee 17 stated: “I also find it difficult to check my own work cause sometimes I feel like I missed some of the errors of my work.”

Overall, the majority of ILG participants have stated their joy and delight at being able to write independently. They value their independence because it allows them to write without being distracted by others; also, they may work and evaluate their outputs without being subjected to undue pressure, such as unsolicited advice and criticism. These sentiments and experiences were classified by the researcher as a "positive view on writing independence."

However, some students have bad experiences during the experiment, prompting the formation of the first code, "suppressed ideas due to a lack of grammar and vocabulary." It relates to the participants' expressed difficulties as a result of their lack of understanding of syntax, vocabulary, and the writing process as a whole.

According to Laurillard (2013), as learners mature and become older, they become more motivated to meet their own learning demands.

Table 8. *Emerging Themes of Learners perception on how helpful Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) in enhancing the essay writing skills for both Collaborative and Independent Learning Group*

<i>Themes/anchor code</i>	<i>Initial codes/labels</i>	<i>Statements</i>
Positive experiences in using strategic intervention materials	promoting self-directed writing skills	Interviewee 18 stated: “it can help you grow, you will definitely enjoy what you are doing and tell yourself, yes I can do it.” Interviewee 17 stated: “I can say one of the good things that I experience is the awareness that every sentence is important, it should always be connected to the main topic.” Interviewee 4 stated: "I learned that these things are really important to know and to have in our essays. We must always check every word that we include.” Interviewee 5 stated: “I experienced to be a checker of my own works and I admit that I am not that good, but I learned.”
	enhancing grammar, vocabulary, content &	Interviewee 2 stated: “It helps me to know what I need and help me to write essay properly. Proper punctuation and proper words to include. Like the capitalization, punctuations, small and big letterings and ofc the spelling.” Interviewee 6 stated:

format in writing	<p>“Proper spelling has makes sense also the format. It's challenging for me to learn these materials but I'm doing my best to learn that because it's for me when the time comes.”</p> <p>Interviewee 8 stated: “It helped me improve my writing skills as well as my grammar, vocabulary, and spelling. I concentrated more on this intervention in order to improve myself even more.”</p>
Recollection of prior knowledge in writing	<p>Interviewee 15 states that: " It brought back my basic knowledge about the basic concepts that need to consider while writing.</p> <p>Interviewee 16 states that: “It helps me a lot because Strategic intervention materials makes me remember when i'm writing some essay and other kind of writing that i should make it good.</p> <p>Interviewee 19 states that: “Last time that my teacher discussed it, it made me recall all of the things that I learned few years ago about the topic especially in writing essay and improving grammar.”</p>

All the participants provided a positive response in writing while using the strategic intervention materials. Specifically, most of the participants became self-directed in improving their own skills in writing thus, the first label/initial code is “Promoting self-directed writing skills”. The participants elaborated that they felt interested towards writing while also being aware of their mistakes by checking their own words while using the SIM.

All the participants also expressed that they improved their writing competencies after using the SIM thus the second code “enhancing writing competencies” was created. The participants commented that they were able to improve their vocabulary by being self-aware of the proper words to use in their outputs as well as check their spelling in the process.

The last label “recollection of prior knowledge in writing” is allocated to the participant’s comments regarding their gratefulness for being able to review their past knowledge in the basic grammar and writing skills. Most of the participants said that the SIM bought back their memory in writing which they were able to use to improve their past works.

In line with this, Cordova (2019) stated that the Strategic Intervention Materials assist students in developing skills that they may not have mastered in regular classes. It can be delivered via PowerPoint, printed materials, or computerized activities. The SIM concentrates solely on one specific competence that needs to be remedied. Similarly, the use of strategic intervention materials in their study was proven to increase the performance of the students in their least mastered skills.

Conclusions

Below are the conclusions made after the conduct of this study:

1. Although both groups seem to have the same “Fine” initial level of mastery in writing, the collaborative-learning group (CGL) has demonstrated a higher writing mastery level compared with the individual learning group (ILG); likewise, CLG has a greater variability of scores than ILG.
2. For the End of Lesson Assessment both groups have shown significant improvement in the mastery level of the students in the writing activities as compared to the results of their pretests. It can be concluded therefore that the strategic intervention used has helped the learners enhance their mastery level in writing as compared to the results gained in the pretest of the two groups.
3. Both groups have obtained an overall mastery level of “Very Good” and the same variability of scores, hence more than half of the CLG and ILG got “Very Good” for mastery level, but the ILG obtained a higher mean score as compared to CLG, thus, ILG obtained a higher mastery level than CLG.
4. Both collaborative-learning group and independent-learning group have shown a “negative attitude toward writing” characterized by their feelings of frustration, pressure, and nervousness about writing, which are due to their poor vocabulary. Some participants, however, have confirmed they're having a “positive attitude toward writing.” They admit that they are delighted whenever they write; they view writing as their way of freely expressing themselves.
5. The themes that emerged from the shared experiences by the collaborative group were: (a) gaining knowledge from peers, (b) establishing a connection with peers, (c) enjoyment of sharing knowledge, and (d) error correction; and fourth theme/anchor code, (e) incompetent peers, (f) difficulty in using the English language and (g) Poor internet connection/ Misunderstandings.
6. The themes that emerged in the shared experiences and perception of the participants from the collaborative and independent group in the use of the strategic intervention materials were (a) Promoting self-directed writing skills (b) Enhancing grammar, vocabulary, content & format in writing (c) Recollection of prior knowledge in writing.

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